

Alteration of the Alluvial Deposits of Wari-Bateshwar: Geoarchaeological Relevance of the Characterization of Grain Size and Clay Mineralogy

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Abstract

This study provides a characterization of the alluvial deposits on the basis of grain-size and clay mineralogy of the Wari-Bateshwar. Field work allowed to examine several stratigraphic sections and to identify several sedimentary units; some of them containing artifacts. During the late Holocene (<3000 yrs BP), this area was already dominated by fluvial processes of transport and deposition. It is also found that archaeological materials have been relocated and modified by low energy flood events during pre-occupational, occupational and post-depositional phases. The identification of mineral composition shows three types of clay minerals, dominated by illite and kaolinite, indicating similar climatic conditions to the present ones. The clay minerals, however, suggest a depositional environment that was dominated by fluvial dynamics and changes. On the basis of this study, it has also been hypothesized that if there is a chronological gap between the 'early historic' and 'early medieval' settlements in the area, some of the key factors for the abandonment of the settlement could be related to changes in the alluvial environment. The paper also strengthens the potential for further studies regarding the beginning, development, abandonment and reoccupation of the settlements in the area within a geoarchaeological framework.

INTRODUCTION

This study, with special emphasis on the sedimentology and pedology through an understanding of grain size and clay mineralogy, contributes to the interpretation of the archaeological records of Wari-Bateshwar (cited in Pathan 1989, Chakrabarti 1992, Pawankar et al. 1998, Basa and Rahman 1998, Jahan 1999, Hoque et al. 2000, Ahmed 2001; Rahman 2012; 2007; Rahman et al. 2003, Imran 2001, Akanda et al. 2005, 2004, Akanda 2010). Wari-Bateshwar is characterized by a nucleated fortified settlement with several other discrete or clustered archaeological places outside. The spatio-temporal patterns of the archaeological places have not been elaborated upon in the published materials. The spatial and temporal character and interrelationship of the 'early historic' settlements within the fortification and outside with the 'early medieval' archaeological places are not clear. It seems from the narratives, maps and table (Table 1, Rahman and Pathan 2012: 39-48), that all the 'early medieval' settlements are away from the fortified and spatio-temporally associated settlements. The questions - on whether the 'early medieval' settlements in the area were a continuation of the 'early historic' occupation or not, and whether the nature, structure and patterns of settlements in the area are differentially defined and distributed according to their individual and collective contexts or not - are remained to be answered. On the basis of the published materials, we would like to claim that along with several other debates regarding the nature of

the settlements and their chronology, the formation processes and their pertinent and essential relation to the landscape context of the settlements are not engaged with and elaborated upon in most of the studies. The transformative context of a dominantly and evidently alluvial terrain in reference to the settlement could be a very prospective area for further research. It is not possible to attend to all the above problems regarding this very complex and interesting conglomerations of spatio-temporally differentiated settlements in this particular paper.

These methods and results in this paper could be seen as a verification processes of the conclusions drawn by Akanda et al. (2010) who showed that floods had played an essential role in terms of the spatial distribution, modification and dispersal of apparently buried archaeological records of this site. These predominantly alluvial processes were probably active during the pre-occupational, occupational and post-occupational/post depositional phase of the settlements. The objectives of this paper, therefore, are:

1. To verify the findings identified by the previous studies through more sampling coverage and characterization of the sedimentary deposits that are contextually related to the archaeological records.
2. To reveal the alluvial history of the locality of the study and its impacts on pre-occupational, occupational and post-occupational phases mainly in the fortified area of the settlements.

3. To understand the past depositional conditions and processes in this area particularly in terms of archaeological data and its transformation through time.
4. To build a few propositions about the spatio-temporal character of the settlements in the area for further testing and verification.

LOCATION, GEOLOGICAL AND GEOMORPHOLOGICAL SETTINGS

Wari-Bateshwar is located (Fig. 1) about 4km southwest of Belabo Upazila HQ under Narshingdi District, Bangladesh. Wari and Bateshwar are two adjoining villages, with coordinates of 24°05'46" North/90°49'42" East and 24°05'34" North/90°49'40" East (Ahmed 2001).

There are two major landform units in the study area (Islam 1991): the Madhupur Tract and Old Brahmaputra Floodplain. Madhupur Tract is composed by a fluvio-deltic tectonically uplifted deposit with altitude of 10-18 m from MSL. The fortified settlement of Wari-Bateshwar and the adjoining area with the occurrences of archaeological places are located within a zone extended from the southeastern to central part of the Madhupur Tract. It is usually accepted that the Madhupur clay or clay residuum is dated to the Pleistocene period (Rashid 1991, Morgan and McIntire 1959; Umitsu 1993; Coleman 1969; Alam et al. 1990). Geomorphologically, Madhupur Tract is closely dissected by valleys with a dendritic pattern (Brammer 1996:24). *Chala* (comparatively high land) and *Byde* (low valleys) are the main features of this landform. Rashid et al. (2014a) showed that after 12000 yrs BP, as a consequence of heavy

rainfall after the intensification of south-west monsoon and related rise of sea level, the amplified flow of rain water with deglaciated water caused erosion of the landform. These erosional processes created the dissected topography of the Madhupur Tract. They also claimed that these erosional activities were active throughout the late Pleistocene to Holocene epoch. These valleys are deep and the high lands have gentle slopes towards them. Archaeological materials are occurred on these highlands and on the slopes of these high lands (Imran 2002:111).

However, there are considerable debates regarding the nomenclature of one of its main lithostratigraphic unit. Madhupur Tract is characterized by highly oxidized soils and Morgan and McIntire (1959) had termed it as *Madhupur Clay*. First lithostratigraphic ranking of this soil was given by Alam and Khan (1980) and they had ranked it as a formation. Many of the authors have adhered to this nomenclature in Bangladesh. Monsur and Paepe (1994), nevertheless, have subdivided this unit into two formations. The lower unit was identified by them as Madhupur Clay and Sand Formation represented by reddish-brown sand, sandy-clay and clay, and the upper unit was designated as Bashabo silty-clay representing yellowish-brown to bluish grey sand to clay (see also, Monsur 1995). On the other hand, the researchers of Geological Survey of Bangladesh have called this unit Madhupur Clay Residuum (Alam et al. 1990). They have defined ‘residuum’ as material derived by in-place weathering of clastic sediment with no appreciable subsequent lateral transport. They have also categorized this as a relict palaeosol (Alam et al. 1990).

Fig.1: Distribution of the main archaeological records in Wari-Bateshwar (Akanda 2004).

Fig.2: Geomorphology of Wari-Bateshwar (Akanda et al. 2005)

The Old Brahmaputra Floodplain is another important landform of Wari-Bateshwar area which has a generally smooth topography with broad ridges and basins. The floodplain is marked with numerous palaeochannels and channel remnants (i.e. oxbox lakes) indicating the dynamic changes and evolution in the channel pattern. Relief and soil patterns are irregular close to channels and include some areas with sandy soils (Brammer 1996:64).

Hydrologically the Wari-Bateshwar area is surrounded by some rivers and waterbodies (Fig.2). The Old Brahmaputra River, Arial Khan River and Kaira Khal are important among these. A few numbers of *beels* (seasonally flooded bowl-shaped low lands or depressions) have been seen in this area. The Old Brahmaputra flows through the southeast, Arial Khan flows through the east and the Kaira Khal (present channel) flows to the north of the study area. The fortified settlement is located 4 km away from the confluence of Kaira Khal and Arial Khan rivers.

METHODOLOGY

Various methodological procedures have been integrated in this study. Field work methods are influenced by Knudson (1978), Drewett (1999), Brown (1997), Butzer (1982), Waters (2000) and Courty, Goldberg and Macphail (1989).

Topographic maps, satellite images (FCC image of band 1, 2 and 3 of Landsat™ image), base maps, and drainage maps were collected from different government and non-government organizations and were studied. In the field, primarily we selected several locations for the study of

sections and for sampling. Subsequently, we identified different sedimentary units on the basis of their sedimentological and pedological characteristics. The work sheet for recording soil properties in the field proposed by Birkeland (1999:350) was followed.

In the laboratory, we prepared the sediment samples for particle size analysis and clay mineralogical analysis. The grain size distribution of each sample was obtained by using a Laser Particle Size Analyzer (BECKMAN COULTER LS 230) and three analyses per sample were done in order to compare the results. The clay mineralogy of the studied samples have been identified by X-ray diffraction, using a Philips PW 3710 X-ray diffractometer, with a Cu tube, at 40 KV and 20 nA. The mineralogical composition of the < 2 μm fraction was obtained in oriented samples before and after ethylene glycol treatment and heating up to 550°C. These determinations were carried out at the Department of Earth Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal.

The method for clay mineral identification consists of two main steps:

Sample preparation to make <2μm sediment oriented aggregates: At first the sample (100gm) was mixed with distilled water and stirred (5 to 10 min) with a Heidolph RTZ 1stirrer. After that, the silt-clay fraction is separated by wet sieving with a 0.063 mm sieve. Then the suspension state was vitrified after using a slower stirrer and duration was at least 30 minutes. The suspensions were, then put in centrifuge tube and a certain timetable was maintained to obtain the <2μm fraction. Then each suspension was taken

with a pipette and deposited on a glass slide, for drying at room temperature. Before this step the glass slides were washed by ethyl alcohol. In special cases when sediments were not in suspension, we used a high speed centrifuge to do the washing. When it was needed, a few drops of ammonia were put in solution to make it deflocculating. *Identification of the clay minerals:* To identify the clay minerals three types of diffractograms were obtained for each sample: 1. in a normal state (without treatment); 2. after exposition to ethyleneglycol; 3. after heating at 550°C for 2h (Aquec). Afterward, the position of the peaks was used for the identification of the minerals and a semi-

quantification is obtained by using correction parameters to the areas of the main peaks.

RESULTS

As one of the objectives of this study was to know about the past depositional pattern of the deposits, the location of studied stratigraphical sections have been selected with archaeological materials (intra site) and without archaeological materials (extra site). Two sections are located at Wari and the other three are at Bateshwar (Fig.3). The physical properties of the studied sections are as follows:

Fig.3: Distribution of sampling locations

Section 1 (Figs. 4, 5 and 14)

Location: Wari; Landform: terrace; Vegetation: native grasses;

Geo-coordinate: N -24°05.633', E-90°49.275'; Total depth: 200cm;

Samples codes : WBT 01-WBT 06.

Unit 1 (sample code WBT 01) has a depth of 0-20cm, greyish brown (7.5YR, 6/2) colour and sandy loam texture. Consists of medium silt and the structure is massive. Dry consistence is loose. Boundary is diffuse and topography is smooth.

Unit 2 (sample code WBT 02) has a depth of 20-46cm, greyish brown (7.5YR, 6/2) colour and sandy loam texture.

Consists of medium silt and the structure is massive Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth. This unit contains some black manganese pellets, 5-15mm in diameter.

Unit 3 (sample code WBT 03) has dull brown (7.5YR, 5/4), colour and is located at a depth of 46-90cm. Has a clay loam texture and consists of fine silt. Dry consistence is extremely hard. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth. This unit contain huge amount of potsherds with dimensions of 1x1 cm to 4x4cm.

Unit 4 (sample code WBT 04) has a depth of 90-132cm, dull brown (7.5YR, 5/4) reddish colour unit has a silt loam texture, consists of medium silt. Moist consistence is friable. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is wavy. This

unit contain some black pellets, (<2% of surface area), 5-15mm in diameter.

Unit 5 (sample code WBT 05) has a depth of 132-170cm, bright reddish brown (5YR, 5/6) colour and consists of very fine silt that contains clay fraction. Wet consistence is sticky and slightly plastic. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is wavy. This unit contains many black pellets

>15mm. Very few white sandy patches (bioturbation) have been seen in this unit.

Unit 6 (sample code WBT 06) has a depth of 170-200cm, bright reddish brown (5YR, 5/6) colour and consists of clay. Wet consistence is sticky and plastic. The topography of the boundaries is wavy. A large amount of white sandy patches (bioturbation) have been seen in this unit.

Fig. 4: Section 1 (sample code WBT 01-WBT 06)

Fig.5: Section 1 (sample code WBT 01-WBT 06)

Section 2 (Figs. 6, 7 and 15)

Location: Wari; Landform: terrace; Vegetation: native grasses;

Geo-coordinate: N-24°05.513', E-90°49.214'; Total depth: 200cm;

Sample codes: WBT 07-WBT 10.

Unit 1 (sample code WBT 07) has depth of 0-42cm, light brownish grey (7.5YR, 7/2) colour and sandy loam texture, consisting of medium silt. Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth. In this unit some potsherds were found.

Unit 2 (sample code WBT 08) has a depth of 42-88cm, light brownish grey (7.5YR, 7/2) colour and sandy loam texture of fine silt. Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is wavy. This unit contains many black

pellets, 5-15mm in diameter, and a significant number of potsherds.

Unit 3 (sample code WBT 09) has a depth of 88-102cm, dark reddish brown (5YR, 3/6) colour and sandy loam texture of fine silt. Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is wavy. This unit contains some black pellets, 5-15mm in diameter.

Unit 4 (sample code WBT 10) has a depth of 102-200cm, dark reddish brown (5YR, 3/6) colour and consists of very fine silt that contains clay fraction. Wet consistence is sticky and slightly plastic. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth. This unit usually contains black pellets, 5-15mm in diameter. A number of white sandy patches, related with bioturbation, have been seen in this unit.

Fig. 6: Section 2 (Sample code WBT 07-WBT 10)

Fig. 7: Section 2 (Sample code WBT 07-WBT 10)

Section3 (Figs. 8, 9 and 16)

Location: Bateshwar; Landform: terrace; Vegetation: native grasses;

Geo-coordinate: N-24°04.890', E-90°49.435'; Total depth: 280cm;

Sample codes: WBT 11-WBT 14.

Unit 1 (sample code WBT 11) has a depth of 0-32cm, light grey (10YR, 7/1) colour and sandy loam texture. The structure is massive and the grain size fine. Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth.

Unit 2 (sample code WBT 12, WBT 13, WBT 14) has a depth of 32-280cm, dull reddish brown (5YR, 5/4) colour and mainly consists of clay. The structure is strong. The wet consistence is sticky and slightly plastic. The topography of the boundaries is wavy. This unit contains many black pellets, 5-15mm in diameter. A number of white sandy patches (bioturbation) have been seen in this unit. The lower part of this unit has dark reddish brown (5YR, 3/6) colour.

Section 4 (Figs. 10, 11 and 17)

Location: Bateshwar; Landform: terrace; Vegetation: native grasses;

Geo-coordinate: N-24°04.854', E-90°49.672'; Total depth: 200cm;

Sample codes: WBT 15-WBT 17.

Unit 1 (sample code WBT 15) has a depth of 0-25cm, grayish yellow brown (10YR, 6/2) colour and contains sandy loam texture. The structure is massive and consists of medium silt. Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth.

Unit 2 (sample code WBT 16) has a depth of 25-65cm, grayish yellow brown (10YR, 6/2) colour and consists of sandy loam, dominated by medium silt. The structure is massive. Dry consistence is loose. Boundaries are diffuse and topography is wavy. This unit usually contains black, 5-15mm in diameter.

Unit 3 (sample code WBT 17) has a depth of 65-200cm, bright brown (7.5YR, 5/6) color and consists of clay. The structure is strong and grain size is very fine. Moist consistence is firm. The topography of the boundaries is wavy. This unit contains many black pellets, 5-15mm in diameter. A number of white sandy patches have been seen in this unit.

Section 5 (Figs.12, 13 and 18)

Location: Bateshwar; Landform: Terrace; Vegetation: native grasses;

Geo-coordinate: N-24°04.923', E-90°49.413'; Total Depth: 150cm;

Sample codes: WBT 18-WBT 21.

Unit 1 (sample code WBT 18, WBT 19, WBT 20) has a depth of 0-100cm, light brownish grey (7.5YR, 7/2) colour and consists of silt loam texture. The structure is massive and the grain size is fine. Dry consistence is loose.

Boundaries are diffuse and topography is smooth. This unit contains usually black pellets, 5-15mm in diameter. A significant numbers of potsherds (dimension is 2cm × 2cm to 6cm × 4cm) were found in this unit.

Unit 2 (sample code WBT 21) has a depth of 100-150cm, bright brown (7.5YR, 5/8) colour and contains clay texture. The structure is strong and grain size is very fine. Dry consistence is extremely hard. The topography of the boundaries is wavy. This unit contains many black pellets, >15mm in diameter. A number of white sandy patches (bioturbation) have been seen in this unit.

Fig. 8: Section 3 (Sample code WBT 11-WBT 14)

Fig. 9: Section 3 (Sample code WBT 11-WBT 14)

Fig.10: Section 4 (Sample code WBT 15-WBT 17)

Fig.11: Section 4 (Sample code WBT 15-WBT17)

Fig. 12: Section 5 (Sample code WBT 18-WBT 21)

Fig.13: Section 5 (Sample code WBT 18-21)

Fig. 14: Litholog of Section 1
(Sample code WBT 01-WBT 06)

Legends

- Potsherds
- Coarse Silt
- Very fine Sand
- Fine Sand
- Pellets
- Samples location (grain size & clay minerals)
- Samples location (grain size)

Fig. 15: Litholog of Section 2
(Sample code WBT 07-WBT 10)

Fig. 16: Litholog of Section 3
(Sample code WBT 11-WBT 14)

Fig. 17: Litholog of Section 4
(Sample code WBT 15-WBT 17)

Fig.18: Litholog of Section 5
(Sample code WBT 18-WBT 21)

Legends

- Potsherds
- Coarse Silt
- Very fine Sand
- Fine Sand
- Pellets
- Samples location (grain size & clay minerals)
- Samples location (grain size)

DISCUSSION

Although Madhupur Clay Residuum is distinctively dated as Pleistocene (Brammer 1996:24), at least some part of its topsoil was formed during the Holocene as already suggested by Sen (2012) in his study of the Barind Tract. The characterization of the study area suggests that changes in depositional environment during the late Holocene (<3000 BP) are of paramount importance as most of the archaeological materials from this archaeological area are dated within this period. The major contributions to changes in the depositional environment resulted possibly from changes in the annual precipitation rate owing to the variation of ISM (Indian Summer Monsoon), tectonically induced channel avulsion and lateral migration of the channels. Another impeding factor might be connected to sea-level changes and concurrent mobility of the coastline as suggested by Islam (2001), Rashid (2014) and Rashid et al. (2014) in the case of the southern and central part of present Bangladesh. From the discussion of Mangal limits and changes in the coastline by Islam (2001: 135- 141), it seems that the present coastline has been subjected to continuous change through delta progradation. Rashid et al. (2013) has suggested similar mobility of the shoreline

owing to transgression and regression throughout the Holocene and they proposed that the present shoreline became stable on around 1500 BP. On the basis of discussion and illustrations by Islam (2001: 136; Figure 9.3), it could be proposed that the coastline was a little northward and the archaeological area was possibly under more tidal influence than in the present because of the greater impact of estuarine environment. It has also been noted that the shift of the course of Old Brahmaputra River between 1776-1850 and onward has had an impact on the regional channel geometry and pattern, and on hydrological regimes. Rather than being a catastrophic event, this shift has been identified as a gradual process controlled by multiple factors (see, Sen 2012). The shift of this channel, it must be noted, has been identified not as a historically isolated phenomenon. Rather, it has been suggested that the migration was a consistent property for this channel like many other channels in the Bengal Basin (see, Sen 2012). In this paper the results of the analyses of the samples must be understood and interpreted in the context of the historical changes of the alluvial landscape under the circumstances outlined above for late Holocene Period.

Table 1: Grain size data of studied samples

Sec no	Sample code	<4µm %	4-63µm %	>63µm %	Mean (phi)	Mean	Median (mm)	1 st Mode (mm)	S.D.	Sorting	Skg	Skewness	Kg	Kurtosis
Section 1	WBT 01	12,47	38,86	48,67	4,59	coarse silt	0,040	0,140	5,490	Very poorly sorted	-0,689	left skewed	-0,376	platykurtic
	WBT 02	3,95	21,05	75	2,9	fine sand	0,125	0,168	4,914	Very poorly sorted	-0,798	left skewed	1,046	leptokurtic
	WBT 03	19,0	34,2	46,8	4,76	coarse silt	0,035	0,245	7,83	Very poorly sorted	-0,39	left skewed	-1,07	platykurtic
	WBT 04	2,8	18,8	78,3	3,01	very fine sand	0,102	0,223	3,57	poorly sorted	-1,45	left skewed	3,01	leptokurtic
	WBT 05	3,4	17,2	79,4	2,87	fine sand	0,101	0,324	4,14	Very poorly sorted	-1,40	left skewed	2,26	leptokurtic
	WBT 06	3,1	17,3	79,6	2,78	fine sand	0,105	0,245	3,91	poorly sorted	-1,47	left skewed	2,90	leptokurtic
Section 2	WBT 07	5,0	44,0	51,0	4,24	coarse silt	0,045	0,055	3,64	poorly sorted	-1,01	left skewed	1,79	leptokurtic
	WBT 08	4,22	29,6	66,2	3,54	very fine sand	0,080	0,116	4,97	Very poorly sorted	-0,58	left skewed	0,549	leptokurtic
	WBT 09	9,4	49,6	41,0	4,21	coarse silt	0,032	0,502	5,00	Very poorly sorted	-0,58	left skewed	0,162	leptokurtic
	WBT 10	5,2	41,2	58,8	4,13	coarse silt	0,05	0,105	3,65	poorly sorted	-1,10	left skewed	1,737	leptokurtic
Section 3	WBT 11	3,1	29,7	67,2	3,47	very fine sand	0,072	0,127	3,68	poorly sorted	-0,90	left skewed	2,287	leptokurtic
	WBT 12	2,49	18,2	79,4	2,77	fine sand	0,104	0,223	3,73	poorly sorted	-1,32	left skewed	2,566	leptokurtic
	WBT 13	2,41	15,1	82,5	2,61	fine sand	0,112	0,324	3,61	poorly sorted	-1,56	left skewed	3,308	leptokurtic
	WBT 14	2,55	15,8	81,7	2,63	fine sand	0,11	0,39	3,78	poorly sorted	-1,37	left skewed	2,812	leptokurtic
Section 4	WBT 15	2,92	31,5	65,6	3,54	very fine sand	0,071	0,127	3,52	poorly sorted	-1,09	left skewed	2,206	leptokurtic
	WBT 16	2,75	24,5	72,7	3,34	very fine sand	0,09	0,153	3,39	poorly sorted	-1,38	left skewed	2,897	leptokurtic
	WBT 17	2,13	10,7	87,2	2,29	fine sand	0,109	0,356	3,43	poorly sorted	-1,84	left skewed	4,632	leptokurtic
Section 5	WBT 18	5,15	33,1	61,8	3,72	very fine sand	0,071	0,168	4,41	Very poorly sorted	-0,92	left skewed	0,941	leptokurtic
	WBT 19	5,6	27,4	67,0	4,06	coarse silt	0,08	0,127	3,97	poorly sorted	-1,04	left skewed	1,374	leptokurtic
	WBT20	3,45	25,2	71,4	3,31	very fine sand	0,09	0,168	3,94	poorly sorted	-1,10	left skewed	1,817	leptokurtic
	WBT 21	4,79	36,4	58,9	3,86	very fine sand	0,06	0,116	3,96	poorly sorted	-0,98	left skewed	1,364	leptokurtic

Implications of Grain Size Analyses: The grain size analysis of the sediments collected from five different localities of the study area shows that the size is <2 mm. The results of the grain size data are in table 1. The particle size frequency distribution of each sample provides an indication of the transport and deposition processes that resulted in the accumulation of the sediments and artifacts (i.e. potsherds). In archaeological context these data are useful for distinguishing between high energy and low energy site transformational environments. Thus they can be used to determine whether there is potential preferential bias in the artifact components. Post depositional mixing and pedogenic processes alter the initial size distribution of sediments. For example, the downward migration and accumulation of finer particles and the upward movement of longer particle like artifacts.

The mean of the sediment grain size ranges between fine sand to coarse silt. The relative frequency distribution is unimodal; they are poorly sorted to very poorly sorted. The samples are platykurtic to leptokurtic; it indicates that the finer particles are better sorted than the coarser ones. The grain size indicates that the sediment was deposited by low energy fluvial conditions, for example, during floods (Reineck and Singh 1980). Poor sorting is also indicative of redeposition and fluvial origin. All the samples show negative skewness, indicating some asymmetry in grains distribution.

The color of the collected soil samples is reddish to brown, dark brown or yellowish brown, which indicates both wet and dry environmental conditions of the Wari-Bateswar area. Reddish soil indicates the oxidation of iron materials. Most of black manganese (Mn) pellets have been seen in the several units of the studied sections. Dark brown to black deposits near surface horizons reflect an accumulation of humified and/or nonhumified organic matter (Brikeland 1999). In most of the sections, downward increasing of concentrations of Mn pellets suggests that these sediments were under stagnant water for a significant period.

Archaeological materials have been detected in the units 1 and 3 of section 1, units 1 and 2 of section 2 and unit 1 of section 5. In the unit 1 of section 1 and 2 and in the upper part of unit 1 in section 5, the concentration of archaeological materials is very low. On the other hand, the unit 3 of section 1 and unit 2 of section 2 and the lower part of unit 1 in section 5 contain a high concentration of archaeological materials. Only in section 1, unit 3 is indurated with a huge concentration of potsherds that probably indicates an anthropogenic influence in depositional processes (a rammed floor?). Within the studied sections archaeological materials are located in two distinct beds of very fine sand to coarse silt. This

association indicates that the archaeological materials are related to flood borne sediments. They were probably deposited in a low to medium energy regime in conditions of surface wash or flooding.

In section 5, unit 1 may correspond to a narrow channel or a pit (dug by the past people for rubbish disposal). Grain size data of studied samples from this unit indicates that it is filled by low energy alluvium. The orientations and sorting of archaeological materials also support this proposition.

There are two different types of fining upwards sequences in section 1, sequence B and C (fig 19), which indicates recurrent or periodically occurring floods. It could be assumed that there were no drastic changes in depositional environment of these units. Fining upwards sequences are very common features of flood plain sediments deposited by regular floods. The amount, regularity, and spatial matrix of the archaeological materials indicate that most probably they are locally transported colluvial materials (Akanda et al. 2005:82). The white sandy patches are located in different units of the studied sections. They might be the evidence of bioturbation or furrow erosion attacked fields that had been planted in row crops (William 1978:597).

On the floodplains of major river systems, flooding plays a key role in the erosion and transport of sediments as well as artifacts and ultimately in the stability of landforms. The silt and fine to very fine sand of the studied samples probably derived from the terrace area and their vertical relation with the artifacts accumulations clearly indicates that the burial by low energy fluvial processes was dominant. Correlation of the studied stratigraphical sections suggests the presence of three main depositional sequences (fig. 19):

- C: This brown color fining upwards alluvial sequence corresponds to the latest Holocene deposition, and is mainly related to flood processes. This unit has low concentration of locally transported archaeological materials (potsherds). It was only identified in section 1. The fining upward sequence also indicates the gradual channel shifting and flooding.

- B: This reddish yellow to dark brown alluvial sequence corresponds to Holocene deposition related to flood activity. In sections 1, 2 and 5 this sequence is featured by a huge number of cultural materials.

- A: This lower sequence is reddish and corresponds to the Madhupur Tract (lowest Pleistocene terrace). It is typical the presence of Mn pellets and bioturbation (white sandy patches). The reddening indicates a much contrasted climate.

In section 1, B and C indicate two different moments of fining upward cycles. A and B in section 3 and 4 correspond to more marginal and distal parts of the floodplain and do

not contain archaeological materials. According to the lithostratigraphic correlation, two different late Holocene depositional events can be identified. Both of these events, during and/or after the occupation of the area, correspond to the deposition of archaeological materials in a floodplain environment. The grain size of the studied samples suggests that the depositional history of this region is intimately linked with the history of flooding. It should be mentioned here that the section 4 is from offsite, as there are no archaeological materials.

Implications of Clay Mineralogy: Clay minerals could be a reliable indicator for understanding the changes in climate and landscape variables (Pal et al. 1999; Singer 1980). The identification in the <2 μ m fraction shows that illite and kaolinite (present in all the studied samples) are the dominant clay minerals with accessory vermiculite and goethite. This mineral association provides (Table 2) interesting results regarding the type of environmental conditions during weathering and deposition of pre-occupational, occupational and post-occupational phases of the settlements. Most of the clay materials are formed in the processes of predominantly subaquatic weathering (Deepthy and Balakrishnan 2005). Illitization is developed by cycles of wetting and drying (Srodon and Eberl 1984). We can interpret the kaolinite/illite ratio as weathering variations. But the association between some kind of sediment (sand) and strong presence of illite, in this case, rather probably suggest a variation in the composition of alluvial deposits in hydromorphic environment. Warm and humid climatic conditions have a crucial influence on the weathering and genesis of clay minerals (Chaudhri and Singh 2012).

Assuming that all the studied sections have the tentatively similar archaeological (not geological) temporal brackets considering the occupational and post-occupational phases, the presence of goethite (only in section 1) and vermiculite (only in section 4) seems to be controlled by topography and sediment's provenance. Vermiculite is mainly the weathering results of biotite (Pal et al. 2012). Vermiculite is also considered as a weathering product of mica in a semi-arid climatic condition (Deepthy and Balakrishnan 2005). The geomorphological and sedimentological contexts in this case under study, however, point to a warmer and humid climate in the region.

Alternatively, we may suppose the influence of monsoon cycles to explain variation in the clay composition, but Alizai et al. have (2012) already suggested that clays are not good weathering proxies at time scales of ~1000 yrs or less. Still in case of a time span of more than 1000 yrs, these minerals could indicate the intensified ISM.

The presence of illite and kaolinite point to their derivation from crystalline rocks containing feldspar and mica and it may also suggest formation from pre-existing soils and sedimentary rocks in the drainage basin. Usually, illite is formed by weathering of felspathic and micaceous rocks that are stable in moderate climatic conditions and remain unaltered during short transport. Kaolinite points to good drainage with the prevalence of acidic conditions, presence of relict organic matter in the source area and near neutral pH conditions in the basin of deposition (Chaudhri and Singh 2012). Normally kaolinite is developed in riverine environments within a certain amount of leaching and it indicates intense chemical weathering typical in low latitude, tropical to subtropical warm humid climatic conditions (Alam et al. 2008, Srivastava et al. 1998).

In section 1 (Figs. 20-25), samples WBT 02, WBT 03 and WBT 05 have illite and kaolinite, in similar quantities. Samples WBT 01, WBT 04 and WBT 06, collected from the top of the sedimentary sequences, have more kaolinite than illite; this indicates more hot and humid temperate climatic conditions (Pal et al. 2012). This kind of interstratified kaolinite represents more humid and high leaching conditions that prevailed in the past (Deepthy and Balakrishnan 2005).

In section 2 (Figs. 26-29), samples WBT 07 and WBT 10 have also kaolinite and illite (this one less abundant). In samples WBT 08 and WBT 09 illite is richer than kaolinite. This kind of ratio indicates a marine or estuarine deposit (Alam et al. 2008), though it must be kept in mind, as suggested also by Alam et al. (2008), that kaolinite and illite might form under completely different conditions.

In section 4 (Figs. 30-32), samples WBT 15 and WBT 16 have an association of illite, kaolinite and vermiculite. Sample WBT 15 is rich in illite and WBT 16 is rich in kaolinite. Sample WBT 17 also designates illite and kaolinite (in low quantity).

Presence of vermiculite on the units 1 and 2 of section 4 indicates less drainage than in the same units of sections 1 and 2. Goethite is an iron oxide mineral, which occurs only in units 1, 4, 5, and 6 of section 1, indicating better drainage (Birkeland 1999).

The unit 1 of section 1 can clearly be taken as a post-occupational deposit that is separated from the pre-occupational deposit of unit 4 and 5 by the cemented and indurated homogenized anthropogenic deposit of Unit 2 and 3. The presence of goethite in all the units except unit 2 and 3, indicate probably to a locale of better drainage during the post-occupational or post-depositional phase after the abandonment of the settlement.

Table 2: Identification of the mineral composition on the fraction <2 µm of the studied samples

Section number	Sample code	Unit	Mean (µm)	Mean (phi)	Mean	Clay minerals (<2 µm)	% of Clay minerals			Goethite
							K	I	V	
Section 1	WBT 01	1	0.0414	4.59	coarse silt	Ki	55	45	-	Positive
	WBT 02	2	0.134	2.9	fine sand	Ik	33	67	-	Negative
	WBT 03	3	0.037	4.76	coarse silt	Ik	49	51	-	Negative
	WBT 04	4	0.124	3.01	very fine sand	Ki	61	39	-	Positive
	WBT 05	5	0.137	2.87	fine sand	Ik	43	57	-	Positive
	WBT 06	6	0.146	2.78	fine sand	Ki	53	47	-	Positive
Section 2	WBT 07	1	0.053	4.24	coarse silt	Ki	53	47	-	Negative
	WBT 08	2	0.086	3.54	very fine sand	Ik	46	54	-	Negative
	WBT 09	3	0.054	4.21	coarse silt	Ik	48	52	-	Negative
	WBT 10	4	0.057	4.13	coarse silt	Ki	57	43	-	Negative
Section 4	WBT 15	1	0.086	3.54	very fine sand	IkV	35	41	24	Negative
	WBT 16	2	0.099	3.34	very fine sand	Kiv	45	37	18	Negative
	WBT 17	3	0.204	2.29	fine sand	Ik	34	66	-	Negative

Legends: K - kaolinite, I - illite, V - vermiculite, G - Goethite.

CONCLUSIONS AND PROPOSITIONS

This study aims to provide preliminary geoarchaeological interpretations of the Wari-Bateshwar area on the basis of the stratigraphy and sedimentology of the alluvial deposits. The terracing of the Madhupur Tract, if it occurred with discrete neotectonic activity during middle-late Holocene, might also have contributed to the relief of the area.

The studied sections in one of the previous studies (Akanda 2004) on the floodplain associated with *Kaira Khal* point towards changing alluvial landscape too. The studied sedimentary records consist of several lithostratigraphic units (depositional beds) organized in fining upwards alluvial sequences. The studied channel deposits consist of fine sand to very fine sand and the overbank fines represented by coarse silt. The depositional architecture and facies consist of sandy channel deposits intercalated with overbank fines; they testify a periodically shifting flood regime, alternating with periods of pedogenesis in the *Chala* (high lands).

The conclusions of this study can be drawn in the form of some propositions, which could be summarized for future verifications:

- Clay mineralogy and grain size analyses provide evidence for the fluvial processes - particularly flood- that were active during pre-occupational, occupational and post-occupational abandonment, post-depositional burial, exposure and relocation. Precise chronometric dates in reference to stratigraphic understanding of the spatio-temporal patterning of the settlements may

contribute to an understanding of the chronology of these processes.

- The settlements of Wari-Bateshwar could be identified as a settlement or localities of settlements in flood zone. It is evident that the inhabitants of these settlements had to negotiate with the changing alluvial landscape, channel dynamics, fluvial regime, relative sea level, migration of shore line and above all, floods. At the same time this alluvial landscape offered advantageous conditions for commercial- especially in reference to its mercantile potential - advantages. This transforming landscape might have also acted, though not so prominently, as a hinterland zone for agricultural uses.
- In an archaeological place spatially delineated by a fortified settlement and the settlements outside with low frequency of structural remains within the fortified zone, the floodplain history may provide valuable insight into the nature of the place. The sporadic occurrence of cultural materials instead of horizontally continuous deposits, and the vertical occurrences of the cultural materials, in most cases, within <1.5 - 2m of the present surface and their poor sorting suggest transportation and relocation in a regular (if not continuous), low to medium intensity flood prone hydrological regime. The alluvial and colluvial processes were concurrent to the occupational phases and post-occupational phases. The 'early historic' settlement(s) could have been abandoned by a decisive shift in alluvial geoarchaeological variables.

Figure 19: Correlations log of the studied sections

Fig. 20: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 01

Fig. 21: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 02

Fig. 22: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 03

Fig. 23: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 04

Fig. 24: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 05

Fig. 25: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 06

Fig. 26: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 07

Fig. 27: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 08

Fig. 28: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 09

Fig. 29: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 10

Fig. 30: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 15

Fig. 31: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 16

Fig. 32: X-ray diffractograms of sample WBT 17

- Attempts must be made for a precise understanding of the spatio-temporal relationship between ‘early historic’ and ‘early medieval’ settlements in the area. The beginning of the ‘early historic’ settlements can be designated to 5th -4th century BCE, on the basis of radio carbon dates, the stratigraphic context of which is not clear (Rahman and Pathan 2012). The history of the settlement has not been elaborated upon in the available literature especially with regard to their connection to ‘early medieval’ settlements in the area. If the two *kundas* or *kundis* (artificial water reservoirs) (Rahman and Pahtan 2012; Alam et al.n.d. see also Hegwald 2002 for the types of water reservoirs) are taken as belonging to ‘early historic’ period, it could be assumed - in absence of other reliable chronometric dates - that there was probably a temporal gap between the ‘early historic’ and ‘early medieval’ period in the area. The grain size and clay mineralogical analyses, presented in this paper, can be used as a premise to understand the gap. Some of the possible factors of this temporal gap (probably of 400 – 700 years) could be induced by the changes in the alluvial environment. Intensification of ISM and consequent flood and changes in the rivers, impact of neotectonism, southward shifting of estuarine belt shore line and changes in the RSL, singularly or cumulatively, might have induced the causes for the abandonment of the settlements along with other factors (i.e. political, economic, etc.). The fluvio-locational advantages for mercantile activities during the ‘early

historic’ period ceased to exist after the significant changes above. The adjoining area (not the same location) was probably reoccupied by ‘early medieval’ settlements’ after another change in the alluvial landscape and rivers. This hypothesis about the occupation and abandonment of the Wari-Bateshwar as a fortified settlement developed predominantly for mercantile purposes must be tested with elaborate spatial and temporal examination by stratigraphic understanding and radiometric dates. This study motivates us to include other sections and sites in future research in order to complete the reconstruction of the history of the changes in flood activity in relation to the escalation and reduction cycles of ISM and related regional changes in rivers – lateral and hydraulical – pertaining to the settlements in Wari-Bateshwar and adjacent area.

Acknowledgements

This study is a part of MS (International Master in Quaternary and Prehistory) thesis of first author, in IPT-UTAD, Portugal. It was also supported by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, Portugal, through project UID/MAR/04292/2013 – MARE.

We are deeply thankful to Prof. Luiz Oosterbeek (IPT, Portugal) and Prof. Sufi Mustafizur Rahman (Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh). We are grateful to Manuela Costa, Janine Laborda, Hugo Gomes, Sajid, Fahim and Muktar Bhai.

বিষয়সংক্ষেপ

এই গবেষণার মধ্য দিয়ে উয়ারী-বটেশ্বরের ভূপ্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক প্রেক্ষাপটের প্রাথমিক ধারণা পাওয়ার চেষ্টা করা হয়েছে। হলোসিন যুগের শেষ পর্বে (৩০০০ বিপি পরবর্তী) এখানে বসতি গড়ে ওঠার আগের, বসতি গড়ে ওঠার সমসাময়িক সময়ের এবং বসতি পরিত্যক্ত হওয়ার পরের পলল সঞ্চয়ন পরিবেশ সম্পর্কে অনুমান করার চেষ্টা করা হয়েছে। উয়ারী-বটেশ্বরের প্রাকার বেষ্টিত বসতির বিভিন্ন স্থানে পাঁচটি সেকশন থেকে সংগৃহীত মৃত্তিকা ও পলল নমুনার দানার আকারগত বিশ্লেষণ এবং কাদার-খনিজ বিশ্লেষণের সঙ্গে সঙ্গে ভূমিরূপবিদ্যাগত, মৃত্তিকাবিদ্যাগত ও পললবিদ্যাগত উপাত্ত ব্যবহার করে আদি পলল পরিবেশ বোঝার প্রয়াস করা হয়েছে। এ-গবেষণার ফলাফল বিশ্লেষণে দেখা যায়, শনাক্তকৃত দানার প্রকার, মৃত্তিকা ও পললের ধরন আর কাদার খনিজের প্রকার ও মাত্রার ব্যাখ্যার মাধ্যমে এখানে নিয়মিত প্লাবন বিশিষ্ট আর্দ্র পরিবেশে পলল ও প্রত্নপলল সঞ্চয়নের (ও ক্ষয়ের) আলামত পাওয়া গেছে। পাশাপাশি, এতদ অঞ্চলের আদি নদীব্যবস্থা ও সমুদ্র তটরেখার স্থানিক বদল এখানকার বসতিবিন্যাস ও তার কালানুক্রমিক রূপান্তরে ভূমিকা রেখেছে। প্রত্নস্থানগুলোর স্থানিক বিন্যাসের সাপেক্ষে অনুমান করা হয়েছে যে, এতদ অঞ্চলের ‘আদি ঐতিহাসিক’ ও ‘আদি মধ্যযুগীয়’ বসতি গড়ে ওঠার সময়কালের মধ্যে একটি পার্থক্য রয়েছে। আদি ঐতিহাসিক সময়কালের প্রাকার বেষ্টিত ও সম্পর্কিত বসতি আর এই বসতির বাইরে অবস্থিত আদি মধ্যযুগীয় বসতির আলামত এখানে বসতির ধারাবাহিকতার প্রামাণ্য নয়। আদি ঐতিহাসিক পর্বের বসতি, যা প্রধানত বাণিজ্যিক কারণে গড়ে উঠেছিল, একটা সময় পরিত্যক্ত হয়েছিল। পরিত্যক্ত হওয়ার কারণ হিসাবে এখানকার নদীব্যবস্থার পরিবর্তন, সমুদ্র তটরেখার স্থানিক বদল ও ভারতীয় মৌসুমী বায়ুর ঘনীভূত একটি চক্রের দ্বারা সংঘটিত বন্যা গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ভূমিকা রাখতে পারে বলে অনুমান করা হয়েছে। পাশাপাশি, এই অঞ্চলের নিও-টেকটোনিক ও টেকটোনিক ইতিহাসকেও বসতির স্থানিক ও কালিক পরিবর্তনের একটি প্রধান প্রভাবক হিসাবে বিবেচনা করতে হবে। পরবর্তীকালে আদি মধ্যযুগীয় বসতি পুনরায় পরিবর্তিত পলল সঞ্চয়ন পরিবেশে এই স্থান থেকে তুলনামূলকভাবে দূরে গড়ে উঠেছিল। আদি ঐতিহাসিক যুগের উয়ারী-বটেশ্বরের প্রাকার বেষ্টিতবসতি ও সমসাময়িক স্থানিক ভাবে সম্পর্কিত বসতিগুলোকে বন্যার প্রভাবযুক্ত এলাকার মধ্যে গড়ে ওঠা বসতি হিসাবে শনাক্ত করা যায়। বর্তমান গবেষণার মধ্য দিয়ে অনুমিত ব্যাখ্যাগুলোকে আরো বিশদ ও সুনির্দিষ্ট স্তরবিন্যাসবিদ্যাগত ও কালানুক্রমিক উপাত্তের মাধ্যমে নিরীক্ষা করা আগামীদিনের গবেষণার অন্যতম লক্ষ্য হওয়া উচিত বলে এই গবেষণা প্রস্তাব করেছে।

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